

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 –2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –4808 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com>

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

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MINDFULNESS MEDITATION: THE WAY TO NIBBANA (TRUE HAPPINESS)

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Abstract:

The Lord Buddha invariably includes the word jhanas (meaning ‘meditation stages’, not fixed absorption of mind) in the full gradual training. According to the suttas, these meditation stages are not mystical or magical experiences. They are simply stages to be recognized by the meditator. These meditation stages (jhanas) contribute to the build-in perfection of the path which emphasizes deep tranquility, wisdom, stillness and opening of the mind. These qualities provide a solid base for the realization of both calmness of mind and the development of wisdom. While they are still mundane, the jhanas (meditation stages) are the footsteps of the Tathagata that form the gradual training which leads to nibbana.

Keywords: Mindfulness; Meditation stages; Deep tranquility; Wisdom; Vipassana; Anapanasati; Nibbana.

Introduction

Everybody in the world wants happiness and peace. This is the reason why people are seeking the true path which leads them to the cessation of suffering all kinds of religions in the world arise because of this search. One great religion in the world is Buddhism; it leads people to the cessation of suffering. Many people are now on a spiritual search for a path that leads their mind to peace and openness. They discovered that the norms of the world which emphasize material happiness do not actually bring real peace and security. Instead, it leads to more pain and dissatisfaction. To these people, the Lord Buddha’s Noble Eightfold Path exemplifies a simple and contented life. A life that to open and free. He taught the methods to free our minds of lust, hatred and delusion and started by showing his disciples how to have an open mind that expands beyond its present limitations so that one can examine with understanding. In the Kalama Sutta, the Lord Buddha explicitly stated that one should always examine and investigate and not follow any beliefs blindly. All of these admonishments were for the purpose of opening and expanding one’s experience so that they will not be attached to any particular doctrine without thorough investigation.

This kind of honest inquiry into any particular doctrine opens one’s minds and expands their consciousness. Then, they can see what leads to a close or tight mind and what leads to a mind which is open and clear. One of the many lessons which the Lord Buddha taught is to first, expand our consciousness by the practice of generosity (*dana*), moral disciplines (*sila*). Subsequently, the Lord

Buddha taught the methods of meditation (*bhavana*) or meditation is to open and calm one's mind and accept whatever that arises without any tightening at all.

Samatha and Vipassana

Here, we should know the difference between Samatha meditation and Vipassana meditation. Samatha means concentration, calmness, tranquility. When the mind is deeply concentrated on the object of meditation, the mind becomes calm and tranquil. The purpose of Samatha meditation is to attain deep concentration of the mind on a single object. So, the result of Samatha meditation is the attainment of deep concentration such as absorption (*appana-samadhi, jhana*) or access concentration (*upacara-samadhi*). When the mind is deeply concentrated on the object of meditation, all the defilements such as lust, greed, hatred, desire, conceit, ignorance and so on are kept away from the mind which is absorbed in the object. When the mind is free from all defilements or hindrances, we feel calm, tranquil, happy and peaceful. The result of Samatha meditation, therefore, is some degree of happiness through the attainment of deep concentration such as absorption (*appana-samadhi, jhana*) or access concentration (*upacara-samadhi*) but it does not enable us to rightly understand the mental and physical phenomena as they really are.

What is Vipassana?

Vipassana is a Dhamma term which is a combination of two words. 'Vi' is one word, 'passana' is the other. Here, 'vi' refers to the three characteristics of mentality and physicality, i.e. impermanence, (*anicca*), unsatisfactoriness or suffering (*dukkha*) and no-soul, no-self or non-ego (*anatta*). 'Passana' means perfect understanding or realization through deep concentration, or perfect understanding of the three characteristics of mentality (*nama*) and physicality (*rupa*). When we practice Vipassana meditation or mindfulness meditation, the purpose is to realize, *anicca, dukkha, and anatta*- the three characteristics of phenomena.

By realizing these three characteristics of mentality and physicality, we can exterminate every defilement such as lust, greed, desire, craving, hatred, ill-will, jealousy, conceit, sloth and torpor, sorrow and worry, restlessness and remorse. Having destroyed all these defilements, we then attain deliverance or the cessation of suffering. As long as we have any of these defilements, we are sure to experience many kinds of *dukkha* (suffering). Defilements (*kilesas*) are the cause of suffering, therefore, when defilements have been destroyed, all kinds of suffering cease to exist. As for Vipassana meditation, the purpose is to attain the cessation of suffering through perfect understanding of mental and physical processes in their true nature.

The Significance of Mindfulness Meditation (*Anapanasati*)

The *Anapanasati Sutta* taught by the Lord Buddha 2500 years ago still provides the most simple, direct, thorough, and effective method for training and developing the mind for its daily tasks and problems as well as for its highest aim- the mind's own unshakable deliverance from greed, hatred and delusion. The method described here is taken directly from the *sutta* itself and its results can be seen clearly and easily when one practices according to the instruction on the *sutta*. The *Anapanasati Sutta* gives the most profound meditation instruction available today. It includes the "Four Foundations of Mindfulness" and the "Seven Enlightenment Factors" and shows how they are fulfilled through the practice of "Mindfulness of Breathing". This is done by attaining all of the meditation stages (*jhana*s). This *sutta* shows the direct way to practice. "Tranquil Wisdom Meditation" and does not categorize meditation practices. Strangely, the current separation into various types of meditation like "Fixed absorption concentration" or "access concentration" and "momentary concentration" meditation seems to occur only in the commentaries but never in the *suttas*. Thus, one must notice this and compare them with the *suttas* for their accuracy.

This is a straight and direct path towards liberation and the supremundane *nibbana*. It does, however, require sustained meditative effort, applied to a simple object of meditation to watch, i.e. the breath, followed by the relaxation and expansion of the mind which allows the mind to become calm and clear without distractions. When one practices the *Anapanasati Sutta* as a “Tranquil Wisdom Meditation”, they find that their creativity and intuition increase as their practice develops. This forms the timeless and universal appeal of a true ‘Doctrine of Enlightenment’ (realizing Dependent Origination and the Four Noble Truths) which has the depth and breadth, the simplicity and intelligence for providing the foundation and the framework of a living Dhamma For All. One will sense the urgency of the fundamental “non-materialistic” problems and search for solutions that neither science nor the “religions of faith” can provide.

The true aim of the *Anapanasati Sutta* is nothing less than final liberation from suffering which is the highest goal of the Lord Buddha’s Teachings- *Nibbana*. The practice of the Buddhist Path evolves in two distinct stages, a mundane (*lokiya*) or preparatory stage and a supramundane (*lokuttara*) or accomplished stage. The mundane path is developed when the disciples undertake the gradual training in developing their virtues (precepts), tranquility or deep composure of mind, and developing wisdom. This reaches its peak in the practice of “Tranquil Wisdom Meditation”, which deepens direct experience, and at the same time, shows one the three characteristics of all existence, as well as, all of the Noble Truths.

The Buddhist practical application of Mindfulness is expounded by Gautam Buddha in the *Satipaṭṭhāna Sutta* and *Mahāsatipaṭṭhāna Sutta*. The Dhamma of Right Mindfulness of Anattā is the refuge for mankind to hate and avoid evils. Perfect Mindfulness is the key expedient device (*upāya*) for annihilating the self-centric ego (*attā; ahaṃkāra*) of attachment and aversion. The aim is to eradicate greed (*lobha*) caused by attachment and hatred or anger (*dosa*) produced by aversion. Both attachment and aversion are engendered by delusion (*moha*). Delusion is false thought caused by false view (*micchā diṭṭhi*) of the human personality and the world. A sentient being is spiritually perverse or insane as he or she does not see the world clearly. Ignorant of the Reality, the ignorant is confused by the multiplicity of the world.

Seven Benefits for Mindfulness Meditation

Mindfulness and concentration will pave the way for insight to unfold. When mindfulness becomes continuous, naturally the concentration becomes deeper. When the concentration becomes deeper, insight will unfold by itself. Therefore, we should strive to have constant and continuous mindfulness. Seven benefits of Mindfulness meditation as taught by the Buddha are recorded in the *Maha Satipatthana Sutta*- the Discourse on the Four Foundations of Mindfulness in Kuru province.

The First Benefit is purification. When a person practices mindfulness, he can purify his being from all defilements. The Pali word ‘*kilesa*’ may be familiar to you. The word ‘*kilesa*’ is translated as defilements by Buddhist scholars. The *kilesa* are of ten main kinds:- *Lobha, Dosa, Moha, Ditthi, Mana, Vicikiccha, Thina-middha, Uddhacca-kukkucca, Ahirika, Anottappa*, *Lobha* means not only greed but also desire, lust, craving, attachment and love. When one of these mental states arises in us, our mind gets defiled. So these are known as defilements.

Dosa is hatred, anger, ill-will or aversion. *Moha* is delusion or ignorance. *Ditthi* is wrong view or false view. *Mana* is conceit. *Vicikiccha* is skeptical doubt. *Thina-middha* is sloth and torpor. Sleepiness also comes under sloth and torpor. Sloth and torpor are ‘old friends’ of meditators and also those who listen to the Dhamma. *Uddhacca kukkucca* means restlessness and remorse. *Ahirika* means moral shamelessness. One who is not ashamed of evil deeds in speech, thought and action. *Anottappa* means moral fearlessness that is one is not afraid of evil deeds in speech, thought and action. This moral fearlessness is one of the defilements.

These are the ten kinds of defilements which must be abandoned or removed from our minds by means of *Vipassana* meditation. The Buddha says: If one practices mindfulness meditation, one can be

purified from all defilements. That means, he can attain *Arahantship* when he is completely purified from all kinds of defilements. This is the first benefits.

The Second Benefits of mindfulness is the overcoming of sorrow and worry. You will not be worried about failure, or be sorry about the death of your relatives, or about the loss of your work. You will not be sorry about anything if you practice this mindfulness meditation. although you have not attained any Path and Fruition (*magga and phala*), you can overcome sorrow and worry or worry arises, you will be mindful of it as it is. When mindfulness becomes powerful, that worry or sorry will stop and disappear. When you have completely developed mindfulness meditation, you are sure to attain *Arahantship*, and hence be free from worry and sorry permanently. In this way, worry and sorrow can be overcome by mindfulness meditation.

The Third Benefit is that of overcoming lamentation. Although your parents, children or relatives die, you will not have any lamentation for them because you have fully realized that mental and physical processes constitute the so-called 'child' or the so-called 'parents'. In this way, lamentation can be overcome by mindfulness meditation.

The Fourth Benefits is the cessation of physical suffering.

The Fifth Benefits is the cessation of mental suffering. Physical suffering such as pain, stiffness, itchiness, numbness and so on can be overcome by this mindfulness in meditation retreats as well as in daily life. When you have some experience in the meditation practice, you can overcome your mental and physical suffering to a large extent. If you invest enough effort and time you can exterminate both mental and physical suffering permanently when you have attained *Arahantship*. But during meditation, you can overcome pain, stiffness, numbness, itchiness and all kinds of unpleasant physical sensations by observing them very attentively and closely. Therefore, you need not be afraid of pain, stiffness or numbness because these are your 'good friends' who can help you to attain the cessation of suffering. If you observe the pain energetically, precisely and closely, it may seem more severe because you know it more and more clearly. When you have comprehended the unpleasantness of this painful sensation, you will not identify it with yourself because the sensation is perceived as just a natural process of mental phenomena. You are not attached to the painful sensation as 'I' or 'mine' or 'me' or a 'person' or a 'being'. In this way you can eradicate the wrong view of a soul, self, a person, a being, an 'I' or 'You'.

When the root of all kinds of defilements, i.e. *sakkaya-ditthi* or *atta-ditthi* has been destroyed you are sure to attain the First Path, *Sotapatti-magga*. Then you can proceed with your practice to attain the three higher stages of the Path and Fruition. When you feel unhappy, please observe that unhappiness insistently, attentively and very closely as 'unhappy, unhappy'. If you feel depressed, that depression must be observed very attentively and perseveringly. When your mindfulness becomes powerful, the unhappiness and depression will cease to exist. So the overcoming of mental suffering is the fifth benefit of mindfulness meditation.

The Sixth Benefits is the attainment of enlightenment, the Path and Fruition (*magga, phala*). When you devote enough time and effort to your mindfulness meditation, you will attain at least the First Path, *Sotapatti-magga*. This is the sixth benefit of mindfulness meditation.

The Seventh Benefit is that you are sure to attain *nibbana*, deliverance, emancipation through mindfulness meditation.

The seven kinds of benefits of mindfulness meditation which the *Vipassana* mediator can gain through personal experience of Dhamma:

1. Purification from all kinds of defilement.
2. Overcoming sorrow and worry.
3. Overcoming lamentation
4. Cessation of all kinds of physical suffering

5. Cessation of all kinds of mental suffering.
6. Attainment of enlightenment.
7. Attainment of nibbana.

The Buddha began the *Maha Satipathana Sutta* with these seven benefits of mindfulness meditation. so you are sure to acquire these seven benefits if you put strenuous effort into your practice.

Nibbana: The Ultimate goal of Buddhism

The object of path and fruits is *nibbana* only. As *nibbana* is *sunna*, *animitta* and *appanahita*. The practitioners of the same are *sunnatavimokkha*, *animittavimokkha* and *appanahitavimokkha*. Path and Fruits are completely free from defilements, and the practitioner makes *nibbana* only, his object without attachment for anything. This is also a reason that the practitioner is called *sunnatavimokkha*, *animittavimokkha* and *appanahitavimokkha*.

Once a practitioner attains, the stage of sotapanna, he has to take seven births at the most in this world, if he does not attain *nibbana* in the present life. A *sakadagami* has to take only one more birth in this world, if he fails to attain *nibbana* in this life. Further, an *anagami* has not to come to this world again, even if he fails to attain the same in the present life. Rather, he is born in some celestial world and through destroying the already weakened fetters like *kamaraga* and *patigha* there only, attains *nibbana*. Arahathood is the final stage of purification, which is attained after the remaining fetters are completely destroyed. This is the stage of *nibbana*. When a person attains it in his life only (when the five aggregates are already existing) his *nibbana* is called *sa-upadisesa nibbana*, and when even the five aggregates cease to exist, i.e., when he dies, he attains *anupadisesa or nirupadisesa nibbana*.

Nibbana is beyond expression in word, but in order to awaken and encourage people to strive for it, *nibbana* has been attributed with a number of adjective. Firstly, *nibbana* is inexplicable, as words cannot reveal it exactly and completely. It can be experienced only. Secondly, in the sense of negation, *nibbana* is considered to be an absence of any and every type of suffering. *Nibbana* is a stage where all desire and cravings are satisfied and subsided. The state of *nibbana* is the most peaceful and once it is attained there is no falling down- *Nibbanapadamaccutam*. Thirdly, *nibbana* has also been painted positively, as supported by the statements like- "*nibbanam paramam sukham*", "*nibbana paramam padam*", "*nibbanam sivapadam*" '*anuttaram Yogakkhemam*' '*amatam padam*' etc. All these adjectives of *nibbana* show that since with the attainment of *nibbana* all sorts of suffering come to complete end, and there is happiness alone and nothing else after that. If the two types of interpretations are considered carefully, no contradiction is found between them. In fact they are just like two sides of the same coin. Thus, *nibbana* is the ultimate objective of life according to Buddhism, which may be attained by practicing *silā, Samadhi, and panna*: or the Noble Eightfold Path.

Conclusion

We are lucky because we believe in the Buddha who is enlightened and who teaches the perfect way which leads to the cessation of suffering. But we should not be complacent. In the Pali texts, there is a simile:- There is great pond full of clear water with many lotus flowers in it. A traveller's hands are dirty. He knows that if he washes them in the pond, they will be clean. But though he knows it, he does not go to the pond to wash his hands, his hands are still dirty. In this way, he passes the pond and continues his journey. Then the question was asked in the text: "If the man remains dirty, who is to be blamed, the pond or the traveler?" Obviously, the traveler. Though he knew he could wash the dirt away in the pond is to be blamed. The Buddha teaches us the way of mindfulness. If we know the way but do not practice this mindfulness meditation, we will not get rid of suffering. If we do not get rid of suffering, who should be blamed? The Buddha, the way of mindfulness, or us? Yes, we should be blamed. If you practice this mindfulness meditation with strenuous effort, you will purify yourself from all defilement and get rid of suffering by obtaining these seven kinds of benefits of mindfulness meditation.

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